

Neural networks and deep learning:

- Some deep learning applications:
 - o reading X-ray images
 - o delivering personalized education,
 - o precision agriculture
 - o self-driving cars
- For a single-neuron neural network working on a regression (for example: house pricing) problem, all that the neuron does is:
 - o it inputs the size
 - o computes this $y = wx+b$ linear function
 - o takes a max of zero
 - o outputs the estimated price.
- When there is more than one feature, the network needs to extend the number of neurons to fit all the features, and then it will get the same number of outputs.
- When adding new neurons to the network, one way to connect it is to connect every input to every neuron and let the network decide which input is relevant, (by the way each neuron represent a node which mean something and the network will decide what is the relevant feature to this node by training on so much data and examples (supervised learning) and these nodes will determine the resulted output in a two-layer network)
- Neural networks are the most powerful in supervised learning applications.
- Online advertising is a big field of applications for supervised learning such as online ads
- A lot of the value creation through neural networks has been through cleverly selecting what should be x (input) and what should be y (output) for your particular problem, and then fitting this supervised learning component into often a bigger system such as an autonomous vehicle.
- For regression a standard neural network would be enough, while for image (computer vision) convolutional neural networks (CNN), and for sequence data such as speech recognition often use RNN (recurrent neural network), also for more complex speech applications like translation more complex RNNs to be used, and for other applications such as autonomous driving a customized hybrid network to be used.
- Supervised learning is useful on two typed of data:
 - o Structured data, like regression and recommendation problems.
 - o Unstructured data, like images, speech recognition (audio) and text.
- Deep learning has been known for long time but only lately started to take off, and that is because the increase in the technology usage, digitization and the advancement in tech.
- And to build a good model for supervised learning you need to add more complexity or use more data in a scale.
- At high very high amounts of data and very low amounts of data, the order between the algorithms is not clear.
- Ways to drive the scale of the neural network:
 - o Data
 - o Computation
 - o Algorithms
- The process of training the network is iterative so it goes in 3 steps:

- Idea
- Code
- Experiment
- **Binary classification:** is classifying for example an image for having an object or not.
- All “rgb” images could be broken down into three layers (red, green, blue) and each pixel in these layers has a value in range 0-255, and to represent these values as one vector we put the 1x1 pixel of the red layer first and the 1x2 pixel of the red layer second and so on until I get to the nxn pixel, then start with the green layer's pixels and then the blue and so on.
- **Notation:** to represent the images of the dataset and the labels of it in a matrix form we take the vectors created in the point above and put them in a matrix where each vector is aligned vertically and the next vector (image) is to the right of it, and the number of columns of the matrix is the number of test sets (I think it means batches), now after representing the images we turn to the labels and put them in a single vector aligned horizontally.
- **Logistic regression:** is a learning algorithm used when the output is either 0 or 1 (binary classification).
- In logistic regression there is two parameters the first is “w” which is a matrix of the images like the notation above and the second is “b” which is a real number, and the output is y hat and it equals the sigmoid function applied to the transpose of w by x (where x is the notation) added to them b.
- And the sigmoid function is $\frac{1}{1+e^{-z}}$
- Loss function for logistic regression: and that is the difference between the y hat and y.
- And it could be represented as (negative ((y log y hat) plus (1 minus y) (log 1 minus y hat))). And it is written that way instead of writing them as (half the squared difference between y and y hat) because the latter function will result in a function that has many maximums and minimums instead of one.
- And the cost function is the average of the loss functions of all the training example (m).
- The goal is to find the values of (w and b) that makes the cost function as small as possible, and to understand the process in a graphical term we represent the cost function as a convex and we want to get to the optimum of it and that is global minimum.
- And to find the global minimum that happens by subtracting the (learning rate * partial derivative of cost function with respect to w from the initial w) starting from zero or a random value.
- The update that happens to “b” is similar to what happens to which is: subtracting the (learning rate * partial derivative of cost function with respect to b from the initial b)
- Partial derivative symbol “fancy looking lower case d” is used when the function has two or more variables, while an ordinary looking lower case “d” used when the function having the derivative has only one variable.
- Slope= $\frac{Height}{Width}$
- The derivative is the ratio between the x-axis and the y-axis, which is a constant for a straight line.
- If you want to know the derivative of a function then you can google it.
- The computation of a neural network consists of two parts:
 - Forward pass: through which the output of the network gets calculated
 - Backward pass: where the derivative or the gradient decent gets calculated.

- The computation graph is a representation of the functions of a network (loss function) and what is happening in every step.
 - When coding to find the final output variable you refer to that variable as “dvar”, which is the derivative of the final variable with respect to any of the variables (working on) in the network.
 - After calculating the logistic regression for a single training example, using the derivative calculus and getting the gradient from the backward computational graph, now calculate the gradient decent for the whole data set, and one way for that is to calculate all of (dw1, dw2, dz, db,j) using “for loop” for (m) training example, and find the result and as the loss function states, and then calculate the equations of (w1, w2, b) where these values are cumulative values for the whole dataset.
 - For big datasets using “for loop” is not efficient, and for that will be using “vectorization” techniques.
 - Vectorization is simply using NumPy library and specifically (np.dot) to calculate ($w^T x$), which gives faster results than “for loops”.
 - Rule: Wherever possible avoid using explicit “for loops”, but sometimes it is not possible to eliminate all “for loops” and it happens.
 - Some useful functions: “np.abs()”, “np.max()”, “np.log()”, “np.exp()”, “np.zero()”, “np.dot()”.
 - “np.dot()” is to apply dot product, and when want to create an exponential vector I need to create “np.zero()” vector then sub with “exp” using a “for loop”.
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- When looking for ways to make code shorter using functions, while processing large numbers of datasets, we can create vectors from single values and matrices from vectors and use functions such as “np.dot()” for multiplication.
 - When adding a real (single) number to a vector in NumPy python, NumPy will sub the single number with a vector of the same number and that is called broadcasting.
 - When using NumPy to sum “var.sum()” we can use the axis option as an argument of the function, and when it equals 0 this means it will sum vertically and when it equals to 1 means it will sum horizontally.
 - Broadcasting means replicating the matrix content as much as needed to be similar to the other matrix doing the operation (+, -, *, /) on
 - Do not use a rank 1 array, means do not initiate an array with a single dimension instead always add a second dimension and if it is not needed add 1 as the second dimension. And in case you had a rank one array you can reshape it (array=array.reshape())
 - If once it was not possible know what the shape of the array is by using the “assert” statement to put your array in the required shape. Ex: “assert(array.shape==(1,5))”
 - Sigmoid is sometimes also known as “logistic function”
 - Normalization: often leads to a better performance because gradient descent converges faster after normalization. by normalization we mean changing x to $x/\|x\|$ (dividing each row vector of x by its norm).

C1W3:

- A neural network means there is another step after calculating the activation function, that calculates the activation for all outputs of the previous step. And that is so in a shallow neural network.
- In neural networks there is a new notation which is adding a superscript to indicate the number of the layer. And a subscript for each node to indicate the place of the node in the layer
- So, to have a neural network just repeat the logistic regression multiple times in series.
- **After calculating (da, dz) you calculate (db, dw) according to them.**
- A neural network has multiple layers:
 - o Input layer
 - o Hidden layer
 - o Output layer
- Hidden layers have that name because their inputs and outputs are not present in the training set, unlike the input and output layer that are present.
- When counting the layers of the network the input layer does not count, and the number of the layers indicates the hidden layers + the output layer.
- To express the layers of the neural network, we create a list of all the (w) in the layer and multiply the list by a list of the (x) and after adding the bias to the result we have a list of (z).
- Instead of looping, use vectorization when calculating the input of the last layer.
- Use even more vectorization to implement multiple training examples on a multilayer neural network.

Activation functions:

There are other activation functions than sigmoid, such as:

- $\tanh(z) = \frac{e^z - e^{-z}}{e^z + e^{-z}}$ and that is true when you center your data, something like a centered sigmoid because the sigmoid has a (0.5) mean instead of zero.
- Rectified linear unit (ReLU): is the solution to the downside of the sigmoid and tanh which have small slope when (z) is very large or very small. $a = \max(0, z)$
- Leaky ReLU: is another function where the value of (a) for (z) less than zero is slightly less than zero. $a = \max(0.01z, z)$
- Relu and leaky relu has faster learning rate than sigmoid and tanh.
- Adding hidden layers with linear activation function is almost useless, so the place to use linear activation functions is output layers.
- Initializing (b) to zeros is okay but initializing (w) to zeros is a problem, because (w) zeros will result in all the hidden nodes to be computing the same function instead of each one has its own function. So, use random initialization (symmetry breaking problem) and the random values has to be small, because if it's large the learning rate will be affected.
- The number of rows in $W[k]$ is the number of neurons in the k-th layer and the number of columns is the number of inputs of the layer.

- **Notation:** $a_{(4)}^{[2](3)}$ this notation means we are referring to the activation function of the (fourth neuron in the second layer for the third training example).
 - Creating a deep neural network means adding more layers using the same building blocks.
 - Dimensions:
 - The W parameter matrix dimensions are: $W^{[l]} = (n^{[l]}, n^{[l-1]})$
 - The b parameter matrix dimensions are: $b^{[l]} = (n^{[l]}, 1)$
 - DW and db has the same dimensions as W and B respectively
 - For the activation function: $a^{[l]} = g^{[l]}(z^{[l]})$ a & z have the same dimensions.
 - In the deep neural network, the layers at the beginning are for simple tasks such as edge detection and the deeper you go the more complex features the layers will start to detect.
 - Connecting the circuit theory to deep neural networks, sometimes “small” deep neural networks can compute what shallow networks with many neurons cannot. (My take from that is that sometimes, adding layer works while others you need to add neurons) and that is true when you are using logical gates (or, and, xor).
 - When forward propagation is happening the values of (z, w, b) get cached, to be used in the back propagation later.
 - There is a lot of hyperparameters:
 - learning rate
 - # of hidden layers
 - # of hidden units
 - # of epochs
 - activation function
- And later will learn about:
- momentum
 - mini batch size
 - regularization parameters

And to find the best hyper parameter value(s) TRY different values and use the one that gives the best results

Course2

Week1

Hyperparameters such as:

- Layers
- Hidden units
- Learning rate
- Activation functions

- .
- .
- .

When working on hyperparameter tuning use random search and don't use grid search

And after finding the best value using the random search you need to find coarse to fine search scheme

Machine learning is a highly iterative process:

- Idea.
- Code.
- Experiment.

When you work in ML you could be **working** in one of the following:

- NLP
- Vision
- Speech
- Structural data:
 - o Ads
 - o Search
 - o Security
 - o Logistics

When your data is in range (100-10000): a **split** (60%- 20%- 20%) is best practice

If you have data in range (1,000,000 or more): your **split** will probably be (98%- 1%- 1%) because 10,000 images for validation and the same for test is enough.

Training data will probably be professional while dev (cross-validation) and test data could be more realistic and not professional. But as a rule of thumb (make sure dev and test set come from the same distribution), because training could be different (professional) but dev and test must be same to have a good model.

It might be okay not having a test set (only dev)

High bias means underfitting (train and dev sets both have high loss), high variance means overfitting (the training loss is way less than the dev set), when both (train & dev sets) have high loss, but the dev set is significantly more then we have high bias and high variance. When both low but training set is less then we have low bias and low variance.

Optimal loss (bayes): is almost zero.

When you have high bias, and you want to improve the network performance try:

- Bigger network
- Train longer
- Different architecture

If you have high variance:

- Get more data
- Regularization
- Change architecture

The “bias variance tradeoff” is not true anymore, given the big computational power and big data availability.

Regularization: in logistic regression regularization is a term that gets added to the loss function, and the first type (L2), works by adding the Euclidean to the loss function. While (L1) regularization is adding the “regularization parameter(λ)” to the back prop loss, and it’s not best because it results in too much sparse data.

In neural networks: you add (λ) multiplied by the squared norm (frobinus norm). To the loss.

The parameters also change so ($\frac{dw}{dw}$) gets (λ) multiplied by the weights added to the back prop term.

How does regularization prevent overfitting: it does so by controlling the value of (λ) and that will result in having linear layers when (λ) is big and having non-linear layers when (λ) is small.

The regularization parameter affects how the weights change during training; this means during backpropagation. It has no effect during the forward propagation, that is when predictions for the test are made.

Another regularization technique is **Dropout**, it works by randomly deleting nodes until reach the (predetermined percentage) dropout rate.

The way I am understanding dropout, is that you generate a dropout Boolean matrix and multiply it by the weights to delete the “in-rate” connections, then multiply the result by $(1 - \text{dropout rate})$ in order to get (a) matrix similar to the original but simpler. And that’s because “can’t rely on any feature, so have to spread out weights”.

layers with a bigger number of neurons and connections have a bigger number of parameters and that makes it tend to overfit.

Early stop is a technique to have better result by stopping the training halfway, exactly in the point where the dev loss starts to increase after continuous decreasing, and that is because the value of (w) starts to increase too much after a while, it has a downside that it does not agree with “orthogonality”.

Normalization

- One way to be able to train faster is to normalize and there is two ways to do that:
 - o By subtracting the mean from every element.
 - o Normalizing the variance. By dividing each element by the variance.
- You have to use the same normalization for train set and test set or you won’t have correct results.

- You normalize to make the features symmetric and then it will become easier for the gradient descent to reach the minimum using a bigger learning rate, while when not normalized we will need a smaller learning rate.
- When you normalize it does not matter what scale your features are distributed on.

Exploding and vanishing gradients: it happens when the derivative of the equation is extremely big or extremely small.

If you have a very deep network (too many layers) the value of \hat{y} will explode **because** the activation function values will grow too large when the weights are slightly bigger than one, as a result of the change in the value of z and when the weights are even only slightly smaller than one the value of \hat{y} will vanish. And what happens to \hat{y} will happen to the gradient descent derivative.

One **solution** to the vanishing/exploding gradients is the careful initialization of the weights, and since we have a large network with many layers, we better initialize the weight to a small value. And for every activation function there is a preferred initialization value, for example we could use Xavier parameter with tanh function. To do that we could multiply the weight equation by a “number” and this “number” is considered as a hyperparameter.

Another technique to solve the exploding and vanishing gradient is gradient checking, now let's review some **derivative math**, when calculating the derivative, you take the triangle resulting from a small change on the function's curve and after dividing the height by the width we should get the gradient approximated. Or simply it is checking the derivative on the graph way (by using the lim definition) to prove the derivative (gradient) is correct.

Keeping the above point in mind now let's discuss the **gradient check** technique, it's applying the derivative definition to the (dw, db) terms after reshaping them and concatenate them into $d\theta$ and evaluate the result, when the normalized Euclidean distance of the difference between (the derivative and the derivative by definition) is around the same value of ϵ assume it (10^{-7}) then we have a great gradient derivative and when it's around (10^{-3}) Then things are bad, and everything in between is judged accordingly, and that would be the answer to the question: is $d\theta$ the derivative to the equation $J(\theta)$?

Notes on Grad checking:

- Do not use it in training i.e. only to debug.
- If an algorithm fails the grad check, look up it's components to find the bug.
- Remember regularization, i.e. remember to include the regularization term.
- Does not work with dropout. So, to use it (turn off dropout, grad check, turn on dropout).
- Run grad check after random initialization and run it again after some training when (w, b) values are far from zero.

Initialization assignment:

- Initializing with zero:
 - The weights $W[l]$ should be initialized randomly to break symmetry.
 - However, it's okay to initialize the biases $b[l]$ to zeros. Symmetry is still broken so long as $W[l]$ is initialized randomly.
- Initializing with big random values:
 - Initializing weights to very large random values doesn't work well.
 - Initializing with small random values should do better. The important question is, how small should these random values be? Let's find out up next!
- Side note:
 - `numpy.random.rand()` produces numbers in a [uniform distribution](#).
 - and `numpy.random.randn()` produces numbers in a [normal distribution](#).
- Initialization with He:
 - Different initializations lead to very different results
 - Random initialization is used to break symmetry and make sure different hidden units can learn different things
 - Resist initializing to values that are too large!
 - He initialization works well for networks with ReLU activations

"He Initialization"; is named for the first author of He et al., 2015. (Similar to Xavier initialization except uses a scaling factor for the weights $W[l]$ of $\sqrt{1./\text{layers_dims}[l-1]}$ where He initialization would use $\sqrt{2./\text{layers_dims}[l-1]}$.)

The mini-batch gradient descent: means treating a "Batch" of training example as one single example while processing and everything else is the same, and the "Batch gradient descent" is iterating the training examples one at a time. And "mini-batch" is useful when working with huge datasets (i.e. 1,000,000+).

What is actually happening in the "mini batch" is with every iteration you go through different set of training examples unlike the "batch" when you go through the whole training set with every iteration.

When the **mini-batch size** = (m) then we have "batch gradient descent". Which takes too long per iteration.

When the **mini-batch size** = (1) then we have "stochastic gradient descent". Where every example is its own mini-batch. And "SGD" could be really noisy, and it will never converge it will just oscillate. But the noisiness could be reduced from by reducing the "learning rate" and one other big disadvantage is that it will lose speed when vectorizing.

The **mini-batch size** that is good to use is somewhere in between (m) and (1) and it will be faster and better than both extremes.

For datasets ≤ 2000 , we can use batch gradient descent.

And some typical mini-batch sizes are (64, 128, 256, 512) and it is preferred to be power of two.

Exponentially weighted (moving) averages:

One type of optimization algorithms is exponentially weighted averages, which could be described as:

- Initializing a variable to zero.
- Using the following function for each new value, the function is:
 - $\text{New_variable} = (0.9 * \text{previous_variable}) + (0.1 * \text{new_value})$
 - And here (0.9 = Beta)
- You can think of the “New_variable” as the approximate average over $\frac{1}{1-\beta}$ days temperature
- And by experiment you can notice that the bigger β is the smoother the line, because you are averaging on a bigger range of time.
- And it works exponentially because if we put the function in a recursive way, we will get an exponential decay as a result of multiplying (0.1) by (0.9) multiple times.

To increase the accuracy of the algorithm above we use “bias correction”.

And Gradient descent with momentum: that is by dividing the “new_variable” by $(1 - \beta^t)$ which will help to give a better assumption to the line of the estimate, especially in the beginning when “t” is still small.

Gradient descent with momentum:

- Almost always works faster than the standard Gradient Descent algorithm, and it works by using an exponentially weighted average of the gradients and use it to update the weights.
- The standard gradient descent causes an oscillation with every step size equal to the (learning_rate), and in the momentum algorithm the steps get directed more towards the minimum.
- Another way to think of the momentum gradient descent is to imagine a bowl and the gradient is heading towards the bottom of the bowl with velocity equal to (V_{dw}) and acceleration of (dw) and (β) is the friction.

$$v_{dW} = \beta v_{dW} + (1 - \beta) dW$$

$$v_{db} = \beta v_{db} + (1 - \beta) db$$

$$W = W - \alpha v_{dW}, \quad b = b - \alpha v_{db}$$

α, β are hyperparameters

RMSprop: (root mean square prop)

- Mentioned in the RMSprop video, that the oscillation of the gradient descent when gets analyzed into two factors, Vertical & Horizontal, and the vertical which we wish for it to disappear is the parameter (b) while the horizontal is the parameter (W). And this description is just for simplification because there are many parameters that could cause the oscillation.
- And the equations to the RMSprop are:
 - o $S_{dW} = \beta S_{dW} + (1 - \beta)dW^2$
 - o $S_{db} = \beta S_{db} + (1 - \beta)db^2$
 - o $W = W - \alpha \frac{dW}{\sqrt{S_{dW}}}$, $b = b - \alpha \frac{db}{\sqrt{S_{db}}}$
 - o And to differentiate between the “beta” of momentum and RMS algorithms we call the momentum one (β_1) and the RMSprop one (β_2).

Adam optimization algorithm:

The Adam algorithm takes the (gradient descent with momentum) and (RMSprop) and combine them together

- The algorithms above (gradient descent with momentum, RMSprop, Adam) are the ones mentioned in the course because they generalize well to different problems.

Adam stands for “ADAPtive Moment estimation”, and in my understanding it applies corrections to both GD with moment and RMSprop and apply the results to the neural network.

- The terms corrected by the ADAM algorithm are divided by the term $(1 - \beta^t)$ where beta could be 1 or 2 i.e. applies for the momentum and RMSprop equations, and this division gets applied on $(v_{dW}, v_{db}, S_{dW}, S_{db})$.
- And after applying the ADAM algorithm we have
 - o $w = w - \alpha \frac{v_{dW}}{\sqrt{S_{dW} + \epsilon}}$ and $b = b - \alpha \frac{v_{db}}{\sqrt{S_{db} + \epsilon}}$ where v and S term are corrected.
 - o Epsilon is not important, but it equals 10^{-8}

Learning rate decay:

One thing that might help get your algorithm to learn faster is to decrease the learning rate slowly overtime.

And that could go according to the equation:

- $\alpha = 0.95^{epoch-num} \cdot \alpha_0$ for exponential
- $\alpha = \frac{k}{\sqrt{epochnum}} \cdot \alpha_0$ or $\alpha = \frac{k}{\sqrt{t}} \cdot \alpha_0$

But it is not one of the first optimization algorithm techniques to go.

Another way is manual decay, that’s when you decrease the learning rate of the model manually after few iterations

A **saddle point** is where you have zero gradient, and it's not a local optima as it shows in 2D plain.

plateau is a region where the derivative is close to zero for a long time. plateaus can really slow down learning.

Hyperparameter tuning:

When it comes to hyperparameter tuning, the “learning rate” is the first one to be tuned, after it comes “beta” when using momentum, besides “mini-batch size” and “# hidden units”, and if still need more tuning try fixing “# layers” and “learning rate decay”, after all that if you are using Adam tune “beta1, beta2, epsilon”

When you are tuning hyperparameters, choose your values randomly so that you will get as many different tests as possible, and do not use fixed values and get little number of tests.

And when you get a set of numbers (hyperparameters) that works best, try to go to a finer scale and tune for smaller changes.

When sampling hyperparameters the best scale to sample with randomly is the (log scale) which is in the range (0.0001, 0.001, 0.01, 0.1), and that is right for the “learning rate” as well as “beta”.

For a clarification: you need to test on a multiple of 10 bases, i.e. test the best value [0, 0.9, 0.8, ..., 0.1] then search [0.09, 0.08, 0.07, ..., 0.01] then go to even finer scale like 0.001 and so on and avoid big rapid change such as 0.9 to 0.9001 because it will not have a result that is noticeable, but scale smoothly.

Because the equation $(\frac{1}{1-\beta})$

In practice you need to review the hyperparameters every sometime because it could get stale, and there is two ways you can do that:

- Babysitting a model: and that goes by training one model and tuning the parameters of it until you get the best result. (Panda approach: one new born at a time)
- Training many models at once in parallel: means you create many models with different parameters and run them on different CPUs and GPUs at the same time then choose the best set-up. (The caviar approach: many eggs and the best lives).

Batch normalization:

It's benefits:

- Makes hyperparameter much easier.
- Makes the NN more robust.
- Enable you to train deep neural networks.

In practice you need to normalize (Z) i.e., you normalize the value before applying the activation function

In case sometimes “sigma squared” equals zero we add epsilon to it and take the square root for the sum.

When normalizing using: $z_{norm} = \frac{z^{(i)} - \mu}{\sqrt{\sigma^2 + \epsilon}}$ we get (z) normalized with $\mu = 0$ and $\sigma = 1$ and to give hidden units different normalization distribution, we use (z tilda) as the following equation:

$$z_{tilda} = \gamma z_{norm} + \beta$$

Where gamma and beta are learnable parameters of your model, so they update just like the weights of the model.

if: $\beta = \mu$ and $\gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\sigma^2 + \epsilon}}$ then (z tilda) will equal $z^{(i)}$

When you want to implement batch norm layer into a network you put it between z and the activation function

The term ϵ is used in the equation of batch norm so when the value goes to zero ϵ will prevent the equation from breaking down.

When using batch norm, it's okay to drop the parameter (b).

The parameter update rule of “gamma” and “beta” of the batch normalization layer is the same as the rule of the weights update.

batch normalization works because it speeds up learning for the network. By normalizing the features.

Another benefit of batch normalization is that it solves the “Covariate shift” problem and that is: when you have a model trained on data with certain distribution, and you want to change the distribution of the data your model won't do as good. So, you will need to retain your algorithm, and what batch norm does in this case is that it reduces the amount of the shift needs to be done. By enabling each layer to learn independently by itself.

What batch norm actually does is that it makes the deeper layers more robust to changes than the earlier layers

Batch norm also has a slight regularization effect, not recommended to be used as that but it's there

Batch norm works on a mini-batch at a time so at test time it needs some adjustment. And that adjustment might be something like estimating the values of mean and variance using the exponential weighted average and apply the result on the single test example. And using beta and gamma that have been learned during the training

Multi-class classification:

Softmax is the layer for multiclass classification and that is by taking a vector as an input and giving a vector as an output, which is different from sigmoid which takes a scalar and outputs a scalar.

This activation function works by taking the exponential to (z) and dividing by the summation of all the exponentials of the classes.

If you apply softmax for two classes, it will be similar to logistic regression.

The name softmax comes in contrast to hardmax which is similar to one-hot-vector.

The loss function for softmax is called “maximum likelihood estimation”

When working with programming frameworks it’s about getting the forward prop right and the framework will do the fit backward prop. And one way to do that is to use gradient tape.

When choosing a framework to use you should consider the following:

- Ease of programming (development and deployment)
- Running speed
- Truly open (open source with good governance)

Course 3: structuring machine learning projects:

- It is recommended to follow a strategy when optimizing and tuning the performance of a model because you might spend too long with relatively no benefit while you could get much better results in a shorter period.
- Orthogonalization: is about knowing **what** to tune, to change **what** effect. And to do that:
 - o Fit training set well on cost function. And to achieve that you could, (bigger network, different optimization, ...)
 - o Fit dev set well on cost function, for that you could try (regularization, bigger training set, ...)
 - o Fit test set well on cost function and to do that you may (bigger dev set, ...)
 - o Performs well in the real world. And for that you can try (changing the dev set, change the cost function, ...)

Single number evaluation metric:

- Instead of using “precision” and “Recall” we could use a single metric called “F1 Score” that combines the two, which represent the “harmonic mean” of precision and recall.
- To speed up the iteration process you better have a dev set and a single (real) number evaluation metric.
- Another way to pick the best algorithm from a group of them is to use the average of all the readings for each algorithm.

Optimizing and satisficing metric:

- The satisficing metric is more like a condition (a threshold) that must be met for the classifier to have a chance to be considered, for example: Running time.
- While the optimizing metric is the one you look for its best result possible in the satisficing classifiers. And for example: accuracy.

Train/Dev/Test distributions:

- What I recommend for setting up a dev set, and test set is, choose a dev set and test set to reflect data you expect to get in future and consider important to do well on.

- When creating the dev and test sets, use the same data distribution for both otherwise you will end up training for different task you want you are building your model for.

Train/Dev/Test Split:

- When the data available is up to 10,000 then we can split it into (80%-20%-20%) but when it's 1,000,000 and above using a split of (98%-1%-1%) is reasonable.
- You need to have a big enough dev set to give high confidence in the overall performance of your system.
- Recommended to have (train-dev-test) neither (train-dev) nor (train-test). But in case necessary then (train-dev) is better than (train-test).

When to change the sets or metrics:

- in some cases, you could have an algorithm with a better optimizing metric but does not meet the satisficing metrics conditions, so we could change the optimizing metrics or change the train/dev sets to fit the satisficing metric.
- Or you can edit the loss function so that when you detect the non-satisficing data type you make a significant addition to the loss of the algorithm.
- As an example, you could:
 - o Set the target (metric) you want to measure against.
 - o Fit the algorithm into that metric to have a good performance on it.

Human level performance:

- We are comparing to human level performance because:
 - o Advances in machine learning algorithms performance made it possible to do so.
 - o It is much easier to work on a task that humans can also do.
- When working on algorithm optimization, it is possible to surpass human level performance but not possible to go over the Bayes optimal error level.
- Because humans are better than machines in many tasks, we can:
 - o Get labeled data from humans.
 - o Gain insight from manual error analysis:
 - Why did a person get this right?
 - o Get better analysis of bias/variance.

Avoidable bias:

- When the human level performance is far ahead from the training error level, then we can work on reducing the bias (avoidable bias) of the algorithm.
- While when the difference between the human level and the training error is very small you can work on improving the variance (the difference between the training and dev set)
- In a computer vision task think of human error as a proxy to Bayes error

Understanding human level performance:

- Human level error is a proxy for Bayes error.

- When the avoidable bias is bigger than the variance then you better work on improving the training set error, rather than the dev set error

Surpassing human level performance:

- When the error level of the algorithm is less than the human level, ways to improve the algorithm performance become less clear.
- Common problems where ML surpasses human level performance: (all are structured data)
 - o Online advertising
 - o Product recommendations
 - o Logistics (predicting transit time)
 - o Loan approvals
- The tasks above are not natural perception tasks (NLP & CV), where humans turn out to be better than machines at natural perception tasks.

Improving model performance:

- The two fundamental assumptions of supervised learning:
 - o The model fits the training set well
 - o And the model training generalizes to the dev/test set
- In case there is an avoidable bias you can do the following to improve your model performance:
 - o Train bigger model
 - o Train longer/better optimization algorithms (momentum, RMSProp, Adam)
 - o NN architecture/hyperparameters search (try a more complex one)
 - o Decrease regularization
- When there is variance, and you want to improve try the following:
 - o More data
 - o Regularization (l2, dropout, data augmentation)
 - o NN architecture/hyperparameters search (try less complex one)
- Fewer layers could result in lower accuracy that is not offset by the lower training time.
- Most of the cases, decreasing bias involves increasing variance so we better apply the Goldilocks Principle: just enough variance, but not too much.
- To account for a high false negative rate, you must pick the right target (metric) that accounts for them.

Error analysis:

- Error analysis means carrying out some processes to improve the algorithm performance until it reaches the human-level error.
- A procedure to carry out an effective error analysis:
 - o Get around a 100 mislabeled dev set examples
 - o Count up how many are 1s and how many are 0s.
 - o Now for example you find that 5/100 of these mislabeled examples are 1s that is an indicator that spending your time to solve this problem will give an improvement of 5% only of the error percentage the algorithm is producing. And that is called a “ceiling” to how much improvement the error analysis could produce. And it could be a 50/100 and that would be a 50% potential for improvement to the error rate of the algorithm.

- Another way could be to evaluate multiple “ideas” (categories) in parallel:
 - o Miss classification
 - o Blurry images
 - o Miss recognition
 - o And to work on that problem you could create a spreadsheet with a column for each idea. And a row per image and start working on the categories with high percentages.
- **Cleaning-up incorrectly labeled data:**
- If the errors are random, it’s okay to leave them as they are, and mean by random is that like human error not some big part of the dataset.
- In contrast to systematic errors, they could cause a problem.
- If you are worried about incorrectly labeled images, then add a column to the error analysis spread sheet to count for them. And correct them if they are significant in percentage.
- The main goal of Dev set is to help you select between two classifiers A & B.
- Make sure that your dev/test sets come from the same distribution, so apply the same process for both of them.
- Make sure to check some examples of things the algorithm has got right as well as the ones that has got wrong, not only one of them.
- It's okay to have a training set with slightly different distribution, but you must have a Dev/Test sets that come from the same distribution and correctly labeled.

When building a machine learning model:

- Build your first model quickly and then iterate. And that happens by:
 - o Set up dev/test set and metric
 - o Build initial system quickly
 - o Use bias/variance analysis and error analysis to prioritize next steps
- Machine learning teams usually overthink things and build over complicated models rather than building a simple and small model an underthought one.

Best practices for mismatched train and dev/test sets:

- When the number of the important distribution images is around 5% of the whole number of the images used for train/dev/test, you will have the following options:
 - o BAD one: shuffle all the data together and split the sum into train/dev/test. And this one is bad because the percentage of the important data in the dev and test sets is small so the training and evaluation will not be useful.
 - o GOOD one: is to create the whole of the dev set and the test sets from the important data and add the rest if any to the training set because now you will be evaluating on the data you want your model to do good at.

Bias and variance with mismatched data distributions:

- When you have a big difference between the training error and the dev error while the training and the dev sets are from the same distribution you may say that you have a big variance.
- When the training and dev sets are from different distributions it is not correct to call a big difference between train and dev errors a big variance, because it could only mean that there are difficult images in the dev set to classify. So now the dev error resulted from:

- The fact that there are new images being introduced to the algorithm.
- And the new images are coming from a different distribution.

And that problem may be solved by introducing the following:

- A training-dev set: a set that has the same distribution of data but is not used for training.

What it is used for is that you use it separately as a second dev set and when the algorithm is doing good on it then the problem with the original dev set is that it has different distributions and that is called a “data mismatch problem”, but if the algorithm does not do well on the Training-dev set then it has variance and needs error analysis

- Variance means: “how well you generalize”
 - There is a funny possibility that the algorithm has better performance on the dev and test sets which comes from different distributions have less error than the Training-dev set, and that could happen when the important data (dev/test sets) is less complex than the training data.

Solutions for data mismatch:

- Carry manual error analysis to understand difference between training and dev/test sets
- Make training data more similar by using artificial data synthesis or try to collect more data similar to dev/test sets
- “the quick brown fox jumps over the lazy dog” is a sentence contains all the English alphabet
- When you are synthesizing the data make sure that both the original set and the subset to be synthesized are not repetitive, so the algorithm won’t overfit.
- Another way to synthesize data besides adding two different sets to each other is by using computer graphics to create realistic data.

Transfer learning:

- It means using the knowledge the network learned on one task to solve another problem.
- Using transfer learning means, training a network on a dataset (pre-training) and then changing the last one or two layers into newly initialized layers and train these layers (fine tuning) on a new dataset while keeping the rest of the model unchanged. And if you have enough data, you can also train the whole model for the new dataset or keeping only a small part untrained
- Transfer learning makes sense when you have a lot of data for the problem you are transferring from and little data for the problem you are transferring to. And both datasets are the same I.e., both images or both are audio clips. And it could make sense if learning features from the first problem could be helpful for learning the second problem.
- One case where transfer learning would not make sense is if the opposite was true I.e., if you had relatively little data for the problem you are transferring from and a lot of data for the image you are transferring to.

Multi-task learning:

- It worth mentioning that transfer learning is a sequential process where the model learns from task A and transfer that to task B, while In multi-task learning, you start off simultaneously, trying

to have one neural network do several things at the same time. And then each of these task helps hopefully all of the other task. A good example for multi-task learning is autonomous driving.

- And the difference for these networks is that “Y” is (num of classes, m) instead of (1, m), but unlike softmax regression, since here one image can have multiple labels, so the loss function sums only on the zeros and ones not all the values
- Multi-task learning makes sense:
 - o if you're training on a set of tasks that could benefit from having shared low-level features.
 - o Usually: amount of data you have for each task is quite similar
 - o Can train a big enough network to do well on all the tasks, where the alternative is to train a separate neural network for each task
- In practice multi-task learning is used much less than transfer learning

End-to-end deep learning:

- End to end deep learning is Briefly, there have been some data processing systems, or learning systems that require multiple stages of processing. And what end-to-end deep learning does, is it can take all those multiple stages and replace it usually with just a single neural network.
- For example, a “Face recognition” system could take a multistep approach:
 - o Take an image
 - o Run a face detector: to detect the human face position in the image.
 - o Zoom-in to the part where the detected face is.
 - o Crop the zoomed into part where the person's face is.
 - o Feed the final image into a neural network so that the system can learn the identity of the person
 - o These tasks can be performed with two algorithms:
 - Detect the face.
 - Recognize the face. And this one works by comparing two images and finding which one from a big group is the match for the detected face.
- The multiple stage approach is much better than the single step approach because the tasks are simpler and there is more data for each task, since there is much data for face detection and much for face recognition.
- If you take the one step approach (end-to-end) then you will have relatively little data.

End-to-end deep learning pros and cons:

- Pros:
 - o It lets the data speak. If you have a large enough dataset, whatever the function mapping from the image to the label then the algorithm will learn it, and if you use a pure machine learning, the model will be able to learn whatever statistics in the data rather than reflecting human perceptions.
 - o Less hand-designing of components needed: that simplifies the workflow and saves time.
- Cons:
 - o May need a large amount of data:
 - o it excludes potentially useful hand designed components. Because sometimes it is useful to hand design some features when the dataset is small.
- A learning algorithm may have two main sources of knowledge:

- Data
- Hand-design: maybe components or features or else things, and it's a doubled edged sword where it could hurt or help but helps more when there is a small training set.
- The main key question to know whether you need end-to-end learning is:

do you have sufficient data to learn the function of the complexity needed to map from X to Y?

Where X is the image and Y is the label.

- To build a self-driving car you could follow these steps and it's not an end-to-end learning:
 - Capture an image, sensor data, radar, lidar or whatever and that can be done with deep learning.
 - From the data captured detect cars, pedestrians, road signs and more this one too may be done with deep learning.
 - Plan your route. Which could include choosing your lane and speed and else, and it could be done with motion planning.
 - Generate steering as well as acceleration and breaking commands. And that is done as part of a control algorithm.

Course4: Convolutional Neural Networks:

- One of the problems of computer vision is that inputs can get really big such as a 1000*1000 image where a size that big will cause a large number of parameters for example, a 1000*1000 image that has three rgb channels will have 3m inputs and assuming the first hidden layer has a 1000 hidden unites then you will have 3 billion parameters which is a very large number so to deal with that we use convolutional networks.
- When calculating the number of parameters for a fully connected layer we must add the bias value for each neuron.
- Convolutional neural networks work by **detecting edges** at one level, and edge detection is:
 - It has two types: vertical edge detection and horizontal edge detection.
 - The vertical edge filter has similar rows and different columns while the horizontal edge detector has similar columns and different rows.
 - In notation an (*) means convolution but in python it means multiplication.
 - An edge detection filter works by multiplying a filter that has a smaller grid than the picture with the numerical values of the picture and that results in another smaller picture, for example (6x6) picture * (3x3) filter = (4x4) picture.
 - Some common edge detection filters:
 - Sobel filter: which gives more focus on the center of the image
 - Scharr filter:
- There are two down sides to the fact that the multiplication of the image by the filter results in an image of a different size:
 - The result image keeps getting smaller and that could lead for a worse training quality
 - Pixels in the corners are used much less in the outputs

- And to solve these two problems we use “**Padding**” so for example: if the image is (6x6) and the filter is (3x3) the result will be (4x4) according to the rule $(n - f + 1)$ where $n = 6$ and $f = 3$. and with padding the rule becomes $(n + 2p - f + 1)$
- Padding solves two problems:
 - o The image shrinks with every time you set the filter on it.
 - o The pixel in the corner is touched only with one of the outputs
- There are two types of padding:
 - o Valid padding: where the image does not get padded. $(n - f + 1)$
 - o Same padding: where the image gets padded so that the resulting image has the same size as the input image. $(n + 2p - f + 1)$ and to find the right number if pads use $(p = (f-1)/2)$ and since by convention it is almost always odd because if the filter was even, we need an asymmetrical padding.
- **Strides** is another type of convolution where the stride number is the number of steps taken by the filter when moving over the image. And according to the rule: $(\text{floor}(((n + 2p - f) / s) + 1))$
- Accurately, **Cross-correlation** is **convolution** without mirroring to the filter while convolution includes mirroring to the filter matrix which means flipping the matrix on the horizontal and the vertical sides. But for neural networks it does not matter since using cross-correlation works as well and simplifies the code.
- Convolution on **RGB** images means applying convolution on a volume because the image will have three channels, and because of that the filter will have three channels too.
- The RGB filter is a filter with corresponding colors to the image channels and equal values between the different layers of the filter and according to the type of filter being used. But it is possible to apply a filter only on one or two channels, not necessarily all the channels.
- If you want to apply two filters on the same image you can stack them together afterwards and that will result for example if we are using two filters, an image with two channels.
- The number of parameters in an image is related closely to the number of filters applied to the image so if we apply 10 filters of size(3x3x3) we will have $10 \times (27 + 1)$ and here the one is for the bias. And the number of parameters after that filtering is (280).
- There is no one single universal notation in the world for the representation of (height x width x number of channels) so you can check for the notation the video (“week1/one layer of convolutional network”)
- When working on a deep convolutional network you will need to apply the rule of the convolution to find the dimensions of the image in the new layer and keep going until the last layer then you multiply the dimensions left and have a single vector.
- When using convolution on a volume $(n \times n \times n_c)$ with filter $(f \times f \times n_c)$ the resulting image will be $(n-f+1 \times n-f+1 \times n_{c_tilda})$ where n_{c_tilda} is the number of filters, because when only one or two channels are being filtered we still apply a three layers filter with a zero matrix for the non filtered channels.
- When we are working with a convolutional network, we add bias like fully connected layers networks and the weights here are the filters applied to the layer.
- To understand how the programs get written you can check the final part of the video “One Layer of a Convolutional Network” for the notation.

- Setting the (p=0) means we are using “valid padding” while setting it to some other value means “same padding”.
- When calculating the dimensions of the next layer using the rule $\text{floor}(((n + 2p - f) / s) + 1)$ here the letters mean: n: the dimensions of the image, p: is the padding of the image, f: is the dimension of the filter matrix being applied to the image. S: is the strides. And as mentioned before the height and width of the image will come from the rule above and the third dimension will come from the number of filters we are using.

Pooling layers:

- Pooling layers are used to:
 - o Reduce the size of the representation.
 - o Speed the computation.
 - o Make the features a bit more robust.
- **MaxPooling** layer: is a layer that passes the maximum of the features under the filter area and passes it to the next layer. And it gets used in deep learning because it works well, and no one knows why it does work well for sure. And the hyper parameters of maxpooling are:
 - o Strides(s)
 - o Filter size (f)
 - o Max or average
- **Average Pooling** layer: is a layer where the features under the filter get averaged and the average of them gets passed to the next layer.

Why we use convolutional neural networks:

- Parameters sharing fully connected layers with same size takes so much more parameters than convolutional equivalents, and it also means that a feature detector that is useful in one part of the image is probably useful in other parts of the image
- Sparsity of connections which means that in each layer, each output value depends only on a small number of connections

And these two reasons above result the ability of the network to train on smaller training set and make it less likely to overfit, and good at capturing the translation in variance which means that if the image gets shifted a few pixels to the side it will still be evaluated with the same label.

C4W2:

- Looking at the deep neural networks case studies help us understand how deep networks gets built and why.
- Some well known deep models:

- **LeNet:** works on grayscale images, you can notice in the network that its width and height go down the deeper we go, and the number of channels goes up. It has 60K parameters
- **AlexNet:** it has 60M parameters, in it there was a technique called “local response normalization” which is not useful, and Andrew does not use it.
- **VGG:** uses a single specification for convolutional layers only different unites and a single specification for max-pool layer in the whole network. And it has 138M parameters
- **ResNet:** it consists of residual blocks, which has “skip connections” that solves the vanishing and exploding gradients, and a residual block consists of three activation layers where the third one gets the linear part and the first activation layer output through the skip connection. Building a resnet enable you to train much deeper neural network. resnets work so well because as a first step it does well on the training set and that results for it to do well on the validation and test sets, looking at the identity function we see that it is easy for the residual block to learn, so the resnet works because the residual block has an identity function that is easy to learn, and adding two layers with a skip connection will not hurt the performance but help it. While the regular nets the deeper we go the harder for the programmer to choose parameters and for the identity function and the network to learn.
 - In residual networks there is a lot of “same” padding, in order for the skip connection to work.
- **Inception:** it is about doing it all and using all types of layers in the architecture and concatenate everything, in the video it all sound like the network has been built with wild guesses from layer to parameters and so on, the inception module (block) consists of four branches that gets concatenated together and passed to the next layers, first (1x1 conv, 5x5 conv) second (1x1 conv, 3x3 conv) third (1x1) fourth (maxpool 3x3 s=1 same, 1x1 conv)

in addition to the blocks described above there is branches that extend from the hidden layers that ends with the softmax layers, and it has a regularizing effect by checking the classification quality of the model at early layers.

- One unique thing about the pooling layers in the inception network is that it has same padding.
- one down side to the inception network is the computational cost due to the large number of parameters, which can be partially solved by adding 1x1 conv layers to reduce the number of filters.
- It turns out that adding the “bottleneck layer” means 1x1 in a reasonable way would not hurt the performance of the network
- **MobileNet:** it’s advantages are:
 - It is less computationally expensive.
 - Useful for mobile and embedded vision applications
 - Key Idea: normal vs. Depth wise separable convolutions

mobilenet v1 consists of 13 block of depth wise separable convolution, then pooling, FC and softmax

while mobilenet v2 has some differences in the block, first it has a residual connection, and an expansion layer, and repeating this block 17 times instead of 13, and in v2 the block described called “bottleneck block”

- **EfficientNet:** gives you a way to scale the network up and down to fit your computational resources and that scaling happens in:
 - **(r)** Using a higher resolution images dataset
 - **(d)** You can change the depth of the network by adding more layers
 - **(w)** You can make the model wider, by increasing the width of the layers
- To know the bet balance between r, d, and w look some online open source implementations of the networks.
- Another type of convolution is the 1x1 convolution and it has in it more than multiplying by a number because it has depth so it will have an effect on the input. Another name for 1x1 convolutions in “network in network”, and it can be used to shrink the number of filters just like using the pooling layers to shrink the dimensions.

- Depth wise separable convolution: consists of two stages:
 - Depth wise convolution
 - Point wise convolution
- **Depth wise convolution:** it means convolving the image with three filters, each filter for a specific layer of the RGB image, and the resulting image will have a reduced size and same number of channels as the original image. While the normal convolution means one layer filter goes over all the three layers of the RGB image
- **Point wise convolution(projection):** it gets applied on the result from the depth wise convolution, and that happens by applying a 1x1 filter on the depth wise result and repeating for the number of filters of the convolution, and the result of this process is an image with the same first two dimensions of the depth wise result and the third is the number of the convolution filters. And as been said before it is useful for lowering the computational cost.
- To compute the difference in the computational cost between the normal convolutional network and the depth wise separable convolution, we can use the rule: $1/nc + 1/f^2$ which gives the percentage of the depth wise separable convolution as if the normal convolution was 100%
- **Expansion convolution:** it is used to increase the number of channels in the image, and that happens by multiplying the image by 1x1 filter has the same number of channels of the original image for many times as needed, and it is sort of the opposite of the “projection” convolution

- Using open-source software is helpful, and it is so good to contribute to the open-source community when have something to do so with.

- **Transfer learning** is useful for getting good results using small training sets, and there are a few techniques of transfer learning such as:
 - o Changing the last FC softmax layer and tune it to the number of classes you are classifying on. then freeze the rest of the network layers and train the network.
 - o Mapping the input training set to some set of activations and taking that pre-trained feature vector and train a shallow softmax neural network on top of it. And the advantage of this method is that you do not need to recompute the activation, every time you use the network.

- Some other techniques of transfer learning when you have a good amount of training data, are:
 - o Is to freeze a small number of layers and train a bigger number than only the softmax layer.
 - o Another way is to tune the softmax layer and train the whole network on your own data

- In general, when working in computer vision, having more data is always helpful, and to get more data you can always use data augmentation. Some techniques are:
 - o Mirroring
 - o Random cropping, you need to pay attention to the dimensions of the cropped part.
 - o Rotation
 - o Shearing
 - o Local warping
 - o Color shifting, which happens by changing the values of the R, G, and B of the image to new values.
 - o Another advanced type of augmentation is the “PCA color augmentation” which works by adding to the low number of the R, G, and B colors and subtracting from the high ones, and you can read AlexNet paper for more details.

- Looking at the amounts of labeled data available online, will find that the data is in descending order as follows:
 - o Natural language processing. You need simpler algorithm and less hand engineering
 - o Image recognition (classification).
 - o Object detection. Use more and engineering. And can use transfer learning for help.

- The source of knowledge of the computer vision algorithms are:
 - o Labeled data.
 - o Hand engineered features / network architectures / other components.

- Tips for going well on benchmarks and winning competitions.

- Ensembling: it serves you when working on benchmarks and competitions but not in production because it takes so much time.
 - Train several networks independently and average their outputs.
- Multi-crop at test time:
 - Run classifier on multiple versions of test images and average results. (Different augmentations)

C4W3 Object detection

- **Image classification:** is saying whether the object is present in the image or not
- **Image localization:** is drawing a square around the object after its image has been classified to have the object.
- **Object detection:** is detecting many objects of the same type in the same image.

Just like classification when the last layer is a softmax layer and the output is the label of the image class, in object detection the same is correct but in addition to the label there will be the dimensions of the bounding box of the detected object in the image.

- So, in details the output of the object detection model will be a vector has:
 - Pc: which indicates if there is an object in the image or not.
 - Bx: the x-axis of the center point of the bounding box of the image.
 - By: the y-axis of the center point of the bounding box of the image.
 - Bh: the height of the bounding box.
 - Bw: the width of the bounding box.
 - C1: indicates if the object is of class one
 - C2: indicates if the object is of class two.
 - .
- And the vector extends according to the number of classes in the dataset
- In case the Pc is zero then the rest of the output vector will be “don’t care” because there is no object to be detected in the image.
- The loss function for an object detection network could be the summation of the squared difference between each one of the output vector elements. Other choices are likelihood loss and mean squared error
- **Landmark detection:** is detecting some landmarks (points) in the image, for example the edges of the face in a face detection network. And that happens by detecting the x-axis and the y-axis of the point.
- And this all happens by running the image in a convnet and after the convnet comes a fully connected layer which gives the output as a vector that contains (one number that indicates if the image contains the wanted object or not, Lx1, Ly1, Lx2, Ly2, ...) where the L parameters are the landmark axes

- Other applications for landmark detection are pose estimation and augmented reality.

- **Object detection:** using the sliding windows detection algorithm, which happens by passing a small cropped window from the image into the convnet and analyzing whether the object is present in the image. And to make the convnet better you can vary the size of the window and the strides of the window
 - One down side of the sliding windows detection algorithm is the computational cost, and to reduce the cost you can increase the stride but increasing the stride will reduce the quality of the detection of the network
 - To get the object detection sliding windows algorithm from using a convolutional network we can switch the fully connected layers at the top to convolutional ones that results a (1x1) features with many channels and the last one is still to be a softmax, in another way to get a sliding windows object detection you can build an object detection network and input to it images that has objects fits in the size of the network window, and this window will slide over the network with the stride already configured during the building of the network.
 - The sliding window algorithm has one down side which is that sometimes the sliding window with its size and strides does not fit well on the bounding box (object). And to solve that you can use YOLO algorithm.
 - **YOLO (you only look once)** algorithm: and this one works by applying a grid on the image at training time and looking into each cell of the grid for the center point of the object in the bounding box to be detected, and the number of cells in the grid may vary and number of objects in the image may vary too. And when predicting the output will be specifying the grid cell and the dimensions of the bounding box of the object being detected.
 - To **evaluate** an object detection algorithm, you may use Intersection over union (IoU) algorithm.
 - **IoU:** works by dividing the area of the intersection between the bounding box and the detected area by the union of these two areas. And the prediction happens by deciding if this ration bigger than 0.5 then you have the found the object and if less you don't, you can increase 0.5 to 0.6 or 0.7 but going less than 0.5 is unusual and the algorithm will not be doing well then.
 - **Non-max suppression:** is a way to make sure that the algorithm detects the object only once even if there were many detections for the same objects in the picture. This algorithm works with the sliding window detection algorithm and the YOLO algorithm, And the way non-max suppression algorithm works is by following these three steps for detecting each object in the image:
 - Discard all boxes in the image with $pc < 0.6$
 - For the remaining boxes:
 - Pick the box with the largest pc and output that as a prediction.
 - Discard any other box with $IoU > 0.5$ with the box output in the previous step.

- **Anchor box algorithm:** enables you to detect multiple objects in the same cell of the grid when working with YOLO algorithm. so, the difference here from using the YOLO without anchor boxes is that in the regular way it outputs [pc, bx, by, bh, bw, c1, c2, c3] which means each object is assigned to a grid cell that contains it's mid-point, but when using the anchor box each object will get assigned a grid cell that contains it's mid-point and an anchor box for the grid cell with highest IoU. And the output for a single cell will be [pc, bx, by, bh, bw, c1, c2, c3, pc, bx, by, bh, bw, c1, c2, c3]. Besides that the algorithm allows you to detect multiple objects in the same cell, it enables your algorithm to specialize better. And the way to choose the anchor boxes shape is either by hand or a more advanced way is using K-means algorithm.
- **YOLO Training:** when training the yolo algorithm the input image will be split into many parts according to a grid and each cell of the grid will give an output includes each anchor box in the cell, and when the cell does not have an object to be detected then all the output will be (don't care), and when there is an object in the cell the anchor with the biggest IoU with the bounding box is the one to be chosen.
- **YOLO Prediction:** the prediction happens by running the volume that results from the training network output on each cell of the image and find out if there is an object to be detected.
- **Running non-max suppression:** after getting the results with the anchor boxes you run the non-max suppression algorithm, to suppress the results with the incorrect predictions and leave the ones that have correct predictions.
- **Regions with convolutional neural network (RCNN):** it comes as a solution to the computational cost required to do object detection using convolutional networks that runs on the whole image, since this one will produce a segmentation map that propose regions and run the convolutional classification algorithm on the segments that shows on the map one at a time.
- **Fast-RCNN:** one down side of RCNN is that it is slow, so fast RCNN comes with a faster approach which is segmenting the image to propose regions then running sliding window detection on all the segments.
- **Faster-RCNN:** is a network that is even faster than the previous one and that happens by accelerating the (region propose) part of the process by using a convolutional network to propose regions
- **Semantic segmentation** is a more sophisticated object detection algorithm that instead of drawing a bounding box around the object it draws a careful line around the object to tell which pixel belongs to the object and which does not. And it can be used by self-driving cars teams, some medical applications such as chest X-ray and brain MRI, where the medical applications are the motivation of the U-net.
- **U-Net:** this network is used for semantic segmentation and that means to classify each pixel in the image to its class, by giving as an output a segmentation map equal in size to the input image that has a class number in the place of each pixel. And to do that the image has to go through convolutional network which will get it smaller and then goes through transpose convolutional network to get it bigger again.

- **Transpose convolutions:** it works differently from the convolutions so that similarly it has an input, filter, and output, but here the input is smaller than the filter so each pixel of the input will be multiplied by each pixel of the filter and placed in the output in a corresponding place to its place in the input.
- **U-Net architecture:** the first half of the network uses a convolutional network that will make the image smaller and the channels deeper, while the second part of the network will get the image bigger and the channels shallower, and to make that architecture much better we can add skip connections between the blocks that has equal distance from the middle of the network and that is because the features on these layers are more similar than between the features on the layers with similar distance.

C4W4:

- **Face recognition:** face recognition systems usually consist of two parts:
 - Face verification:
 - Input: image and ID.
 - Output: whether the input image is that of the claimed person.
 - Face recognition:
 - Have a database of K persons
 - Get an input image
 - Output ID if the image is any of the K persons (or “not recognized”)

- **One-shot learning problem:**
 - The problem of having one training example of the object to be recognized, and the model must learn to recognize it again from that example.
 - To solve the one-shot learning, you can train the model to learn a “similarity” function. And the similarity function works by inputting two images and output the degree of difference between the two images. And when you have a database and want to recognize an image you can compare for similarity between the image and all the images in the database
 - When you add another object (person) to the database it will be easy to do so using one-shot learning while when adding a new object to a CNN database you need to re-train the network.

- To find about the similarity and difference between two faces it is a good choice to use a **Siamese network**. Which is based on a paper called deepface
- The Siamese network works as follows:

- Takes an image as input and gives a feature vector of 128 numbers (encoding of the input) as output.
- Do the point above for two or more images.
- Compare the feature vectors of the images.
- Then you can define the distance between these two images as the norm of the difference of these two images.
- The smaller the distance between the vectors that means it's of the same person and the larger the difference means the images of a different person.
- One way to train the network to give you the feature vector of the network is to run the gradient decent on the **Triplet loss** function. And the triplet loss function is based on a paper called FaceNet
- The name Triplet loss comes from the fact that you will always be looking at three images at one time, one is the Anchor image, the second is a positive image and the third is a negative image.
- And what you want is that the distance between the anchor and the positive image to be smaller than the distance between the anchor and the negative image.
- To avoid having the network outputting zero or any other trivial output we could add a margin (alpha) to the equation of the distance. And what this margin does is that it pushes the difference between the (anchor-positive) and (anchor-negative) distances to be bigger and give better results.
- The triplet loss function is the result of taking the max() of the difference between the distances and zero
- When training the network using the triplet loss function use triplets that are hard to train on so the gradient decent will be improving the performance of the network, otherwise if you use random triplets the network will not have good training.

- Face recognition can also be posed as a straight binary classification problem, and that happens by using the Siamese network to compute the feature vector for two pictures and connect these vectors to a logistic regression unit then take the output of the LR where 1 means the images are of the same person and zero if the images are of the same person.
- And to calculate the output \hat{y} you can use the same function $(wx+b)$ but sub x by the difference of the feature vectors element wise. And the difference here gets calculated by the “kai squared formula”

Neural style transfer:

- The transfer happens by combining the content of one image with the style of another to have a new image.
- In neural style transfer we train the pixels of the image and no the parameters of the network.

- What are deep ConvNets learning, let's take for an example a single unit from the first layer of the convnet and look at what this unit is seeing, now find the nine image patches that maximize the unit's activation, then do the same thing for all the units in the layer.
- And what you can see from the visualization of the units of the layers is that the deeper you go the more sophisticated the patches and the features get.
- **Loss function:** for the neural style transfer to calculate the loss function you add two loss functions:
 - o A content loss function: where it measures the similarity between the content of the generated image and the content of the content image, multiplied by the hyperparameter Alpha.
 - o A style loss function: it measures the similarity between the style of the generated image and the style of the style image, multiplied by the hyperparameter Beta.
- To find the style transferred image:
 - o Initialize the image 100 x 100 x 3
 - o Use gradient descent to minimize the loss of the generated image
- **Content cost function:**
 - o Choose a layer not too deep and not too shallow in your network to compute the content loss.
 - o Use a pre-trained convnet
 - o Now find the activations of the layer L (which is described in the first point) on the images –content image and generated image- and if the activations are similar then the content of the images are similar too
- **Style cost function:**
 - o Define style as the correlation between activations across channels.
 - o And what it means for the channels to be correlated, is that when one of them is present the other will be present too, and when uncorrelated you will find one of them without the other.
 - o And what you will do is calculate the style matrix and it is $G = n_c \times n_c$
 - o In linear algebra we will be calculating the “gram matrix” for the style image and the generated image
 - o The style loss is the squared difference between these two matrices
- **Generalizing to 1D and 3D data:**
 - o For example, processing EKG data of a patient is 1D data processing, and for that you can use 1Dconv layers
 - o And an example for 3D data is a CT scan where it is a 3D version of an x-ray scan

C5W1:

- Some applications of RNNs:
 - o Speech recognition
 - o Music generation
 - o Sentiment classification
 - o DNA sequence analysis
 - o Machine translation
 - o Video activity recognition
 - o Name- entity recognition is when a system search for names in a sentence, and it is used in search engines for example
- To represent the position of the word (element) in a sentence (sequence) you can superscript the index of the word in a triangular bracket.
- When building a dictionary, we can use one-hot vector to represent the words we want to include, and if you find in the dataset a word that is not in the vocabulary you can just create a word (token) called <unknown> to represent unknown words.

- Some problems RNNs solve:
 - o Sometimes the inputs and outputs can be different lengths in different examples. Maybe padding all the examples with zeros to be equal to the biggest one can be useful
 - o The network does not share features learned across different positions of text.
 - o When working on a dataset with many features the input layer will have to be too big, for example a dictionary of 10,000 words and a dataset of 100,000 examples will result in a billion-feature input layer.
- Recurrent neural networks work by inputting the first word and predicting it, then passing the activation to the next word and predicting it and until the dataset ends, and this is the process for only when the dataset has $T_x = T_y$
- The parameters in a neural network are all the same for all training examples.
- The fact that the RNN passes the activation of a layer to the next one sometimes causes an issue where a word could have different meanings and could come as a name or a verb with each time it occurs and the solution for that is using bidirectional recurrent neural network, “BRNN” instead of unidirectional

- When working with frameworks, the framework itself will take care of the back propagation but it is useful to understand it roughly.
- Some different RNN network architecture:
 - o Many-to-many: when $T_x = T_y$, such as name-entity recognition
 - o Many-to-many: when $T_x \neq T_y$, such as machine translation, which have two distinct parts encoder and decoder.
 - o Many-to-one: when you have many inputs, and one output such as a decision, for example sentiment analysis in a movie recommendation system.
 - o One-to-one: which is the simplest form of having one input and one output.

- One-to-many: where there are one input and many outputs, for example music generation
- Language modeling,
 - speech recognition:
 - What a language model does is that it estimates the probability of the sentences it gets as an input and gives a higher result for the sentence that is most likely to be the correct one.
 - To build a language model, you need to:
 - Training set which is a big corpus of text
 - Tokenize the sentences of the dataset text:
 - Decide if punctuation is a token or not.
 - Map the tokens (words) to your vocabulary (dictionary for example)
 - Model when sentences end, by adding an extra token <EOS> to the end of each sentence
 - Translate the uncommon words to <unknown>.
 - Build a RNN network to find the probabilities:
 - Each token will be compared to every token in the vocabulary, to find which one is the match for it.
 - In the next time step the model predicts the token, but this time given the token or tokens came before it
 - Define the cost function.
 - After training, to know what has been learned you can sample novel sequences, and that is done by:
 - Inputting zero in the first-time step as activation and input and sample from the result randomly.
 - Take the result of the past step and pass it as input in this time step then sample randomly from the result.
 - Repeat the past step until you get <EOS> token and then you have a sample sequence from the network
 - You can reject any <unknown> sample to make sure you have a sentence in the final result
- Another type of language models is the character-level language model where instead of words it looks for characters and its vocabulary is:
 - Alphabet: a, b, c, d.....
 - Numbers: 1, 2, 3, 4,
 - Punctuation: ., ', ;
 - Capital alphabet: A, B, C, D,

One upside of character level model is that you will not have an <unknown> token, and the main disadvantage is that you end up with much longer language sequences, and a model less efficient in detecting longer token dependencies, also it is more computationally expensive

- RNN vanishing gradients: already learned how RNNs get the activations from the previous time-step to make the decision so when we have a long RNN network the gradient will of the early layers will vanish for the later ones. And a solution for it is the gated recurrent unit (GRU)
- For the exploding gradient with RNNs, it is a less common problem but when it happens it is also very bad, and it is easier to spot, as a solution we apply gradient clipping.

- **Gated recurrent unit (GRU):**
 - First let's explain the RNN unit, which is made up of an activation (tanh) that receives an input and a previous activation value, concatenated together and the result of the activation function gets passed to the next time step and to a softmax function the will give the prediction as a result.
 - You can think of the GRU as a RNN unit but with a gate (Γ) which is equal to either zero or one that allow or stop the input value from being updated with the new activation, and sometimes a certain activation does not need to be updated in the direct next time step because the subject of the sentence might change for example. And that allow the network to solve the vanishing gradient problem by passing the activation for many time steps and reserving long dependencies
 - Another gate that is added to the GRU that does not exist in the RNN is the relative gamma which decides how relevant the activation of the previous layer to the current layer.
 - GRU is a common version of the RNN but it is not the only one for example you can build your own RNN and use it for your application

- **Long short-term memory (LSTM):**
 - For the LSTM it is like GRUs but has some differences such as:
 - It has another type of gates that will determine the "forgetting" level of the layer and take the place of $(1 - \Gamma)$.
 - The activation function has a different value.
 - It is much more complex than GRU
- If you have to pick one of the LSTM or GRU to use, the LSTM is recommended because it is more common

- **Bidirectional RNNs:** are the type of RNN that takes from the past and the next time steps.
 - The BRNN works by going forward and calculate the activation for each time step then going backward and calculate the activations and after that it gives the output activations
 - You can use BRNN with LSTM or GRU and it works fine

- The disadvantage of BRNN is that you need to have the full sequence before making predictions anywhere

- **Deep RNNs:** to get better results you sometimes stack RNN layers one over the other and having more than 3 layers is probably too much, one could work and the more you add it gets better until it does not.
- Sometimes you might see a network connected on the output of each time-step of the RNN and this network layers are not connected horizontally.

- Word representations:
 - **One-hot representation:** has the issue of the lack of generalization, i.e., it does not know the popular real-life things and that is because the inner product of two one-hot vectors is zero.
 - **Featurized representation:** word embedding, which is representing the word with a set of chosen adjectives, verbs, names, and so on which gives relations between the different words, for example: apple is 0.99 fruit, 0.0 clothes, -1 man, 0.99 food, and so on for a reasonable number of features. And do that for all the words in your vocabulary. And this representation is useful in predicting a sentence completion or filling a blank. When visualizing the word embedding in 2D it will look like clusters of similar things the closer the elements the more related in real life.

- **Using word embedding in NLP:** one application is named entity recognition for example, where it can learn from reading large amounts of text from the internet and building the correct embeddings, and for named entity recognition it is better to use bidirectional RNN than unidirectional. Which is an application of transfer learning, which takes the following steps:
 - Learn word embedding from large text corpus. (1-100B words). Or download pre-trained embedding online.
 - Transfer embeddings for a new task with smaller training set. (Say, 100k words)
 - Optional: continue to finetune the word embedding with new data. It is needed for big data sets only, not small ones.
- **Transfer learning in NLP** is useful in the following tasks:
 - named entity recognition.
 - text summarization.
 - co-reference resolution.
 - parsing.
- Word embedding has a relationship to face encoding (using Siamese network): where the two concepts are similar but have few differences, such as:

- In image embedding, you use one network to produce an embedding for each new image it receives, while in word embedding you have a vocabulary, and you need to learn embeddings for each and every one of them.
- Encoding and embedding can be used interchangeably
- Properties of word embeddings:
 - Analogies: which means calculating the differences between similar combinations of words in order to fill a blank or come up with a new combination, it can be calculated through finding the word that gives the maximum possible similarity between a word and another to be a similar combination to a second different combination.
 - Most common similarity function is “cos” similarity, which can be found by calculating the distance of the two vectors.
 - Euclidean distance: which a measure of dissimilarity
- When you implement an algorithm for word embedding what you end up with is an **embedding matrix**. Where the columns are the words, and the rows are the embeddings, and each word will have a one-hot vector that get multiplied by the matrix to get the embeddings for the word.

- When studying the algorithms of **learning word embeddings**, we start from older, less efficient and more complex ones to develop an understanding of how the algorithm works, then we study the new, compact, more efficient ones.
- One set up is to use neural networks to predict a word as part of a sentence, and that comes in different possible options:
 - Feeding the present words embeddings of the sentence into the neural network and use softmax layer as the last layer, which will give the embedding vector of the missing word as an output.
 - Feeding a fixed number of past words from the sentence (a word history) for example 4 or 1 word (context) into the network and predicting the missing one (target) from a softmax. And this choice enables you to deal with a variety of sentences.
 - Feeding a fixed number of past and future words from the sentence, to be able to predict the word in the middle
 - Feed the sentence for the algorithm to use a nearby word, in finding and predicting the missing one.
- **Word2Vec:**
 - In the **skip-grams** algorithm the network chooses the context word(s) randomly and chooses the target word also randomly, in order to learn the embeddings and build a supervised problem by creating connections between the different word of the vocabulary.
 - There are some issues in using the skip-grams algorithm:
 - Computational speed: and the solution is using hierarchical softmax where the more common words put higher in the hierarchy which uses a log function to softmax instead of a linear one

- In reality the context is not chosen entirely random but there are some heuristics to enable sampling the less common words as well as the more common ones
 - **Negative sampling:** is another algorithm to learn the embeddings of the words and it works by the following:
 - Take a context word from the input sentence.
 - Take a different target word from the sentence.
 - Assign 1 to the pair of words to indicate that the pair is connected
 - Then take another target word but this time from the vocabulary and assign 0 to the pair to indicate that the pair is not connected and keep repeating this step for a certain number of times big if the dataset is small and vice versa.
 - And the steps above happen during the training but not prediction, where in prediction you will input a pair of words and predict 1 or 0.
 - Using the negative sampling algorithm, we can save the computational costs and that is by needing to train on only the certain number of words instead of the whole vocabulary.
 - So, after finding that choosing the target randomly or taking the uniform distribution could result a not fair advantage for the more common words, the researchers decided to use the selection to the power of $(3/4)$
- **GloVe (Global Vectors For Word Representation) word vector:**
 - It works by counting the number of times the words (context, target) appear close to each other, and the relationship might be symmetrical means $X_{ij} = X_{ji}$.
 - In the equation of the model there is a weighting term to decide the weight of each word and make the less common and more common words more balanced.
 - The embeddings are found according to some equation in the slides.
 - Sentiment classification: is about finding if a piece of text indicates positive emotion or negative emotion (like or dislike)
 - It works by inputting the embeddings of a sentence or a report into a network to get its average then input into a softmax layer and the output could be the rating or the number of stars of the report, but this is not the best classifier because it does not understand the context, so you can instead use RNN for sentiment classification.
 - You can use RNN many-to-one architecture by inputting the embeddings into the RNN and then A softmax will give the rating as an output
 - One problem in word embeddings is that it has **biases** such as gender, ethnicity, age, sexual orientation and many more. And it comes from the biases in the text used to train the model.

To address the biases in word embeddings:

- Identify bias direction: by taking pairs of words of opposite gender or ethnicity and subtract the embeddings from one another, to find out what is the direction of the bias.
- Neutralize: for every word that is not definitional, project to get rid of bias. Definitional here means not explicit in its gender, ethnicity or so, such as the professions.

- Equalize pairs. Means make the distance of both genders form a certain profession for example equal.

- **Sequence-to-sequence (many-to-many) models:**
 - o some of it's applications are:
 - Machine translation: works by inputting the sentence in one language and outputting a different sentence in another language. And it has an encoding model and a decoding model
 - Speech recognition
 - Beam search detection
 - Trigger word detection
 - Image captioning: happens by getting output vector (before the softmax) for the image from a convolutional network such as AlexNet and then inputting this vector into a RNN that will generate the caption based on the vector been input.
 - o To generate the best caption instead of a random caption, you can think of a machine translation model as a conditional language model, because it has to have an encoding network that will generate a representation to the input, in other words it will give the output sentence conditioned on the input sentence, and to give the best output you have to produce many sentences and return the one with highest probability.
 - o To find the sentence with highest probability, we could use:
 - **Greedy search:** which works by picking one word at a time and choosing the word that have the highest probability in the first place, then for the second word in the sentence choose the word with the highest probability and for the third word in the sentence choose the word with the highest probability and so on. But it does not work because
 - it might result in a more complex and longer sentence to be outputted because its words have the highest probability instead of the best English sentence.
 - And it may use so big computational resources because it must go through the whole vocabulary to pick each word of the sentence.
 - o **Beam search:** what beam search do instead of greedy search, is that when choosing the best first word in the sentence, it will pick more than one word from the vocabulary and according to the “beam width” variable, and this first step happen in the encoder and the first block of the decoder,

Now the second step of beam search is choosing the (first, second) words in the vocabulary with the highest probability, after searching all the possibilities from the vocabulary for all the words been chosen in the first step.

then in the third step the algorithm will take the pairs resulted from the previous step and from vocabulary choose the best word that will give the best three-word sentences and count equal to the beam width

and keep going until getting <EOS> token

when the “beam width” equals one then we have the greedy search algorithm

- **Refinements to beam search:** such as:
 - Length normalization: instead of multiplying the probabilities of the words to get the sentence probability which could lead to a numerical underflow, we could use summation of logarithm. And after that the calculation will fail for longer sentences, because summation for negative logs will keep getting smaller, so to solve that we multiply by the inverse of the number of words in the sentence to the power of alpha, which is another hyperparameter between 1 and 0. and the sentence with the highest probability will be outputted as a translation.
- **Which value of beam width to choose:** small beam width gives faster bad results, while large beam width gives good results slowly.
- Unlike Breadth first search (BFS) and depth first search (DFS) beam width search runs much faster but with less accuracy to find the maximum
- **Error analysis in beam search:** first you need to figure out whether it is RNN is the one to blame or beam search algorithm, and to do that:
 - We can decide that the fault is from the beam search algorithm if the probability (in English quality) of the human translation is better than the machine translation
 - The second case that the human translation is better, but the RNN predicted that the machine is better instead of the human
 - You need to run many examples and analyze the error in all of them and then decide which one is the cause of the error, to spend your time wisely

- Machine translation algorithms sometimes give equally well translations to the same sentence, and to decide the accuracy of such a model we use **bleu score**.
- “Bleu” stands for (bilingual evaluation understudy) and it works by building a model and evaluating its output by humans and setting a score to it. And there are many ways to measure the bleu score:
 - measuring the precision (using unigram) to it is not useful so could use modified precision which works by counting the number of times the word appears in the sentence in addition to the regular precision.
 - Using bigrams, which means (pairs of words), and those pairs consists of two words directly next to each other.

- And you could use the n-gram version where you decide the number of words required to be next to each other, and the best result possible is to get a precision of one.
- **Attention model:**
 - As mentioned earlier, when sequences (sentences) get so long the RNN model starts suffering after few words and it will start giving worse results, and here comes the attention model where it works by focusing on smaller sequences at the time.
 - To build an attention model we use a bidirectional RNN and will use another RNN (hidden layer) to generate the translation.
 - What the model is going to be doing is calculating a set of attention weight (alpha) in the bidirectional layer and pass them to the hidden layer for it to choose which words to pay attention to.
 - And from the context the hidden layer will generate the output word
 - What the alpha is doing is giving a parameter to how much the hidden layer should depend on the i th word in the input while generating the j th word in the output.
- Implementing an attention model: you can implement the model described above and train it with gradient decent, but a negative side of the model is that it run with a quadratic cost of time
 - Another application of attention models added to machine translation is the image captioning
- Speech recognition: which it works by getting an audio clip as input, and giving a transcript as an output, and simply “audio” is just the changes in air pressure against time.
 - It could work by generating “spectrograms” which is a group of colors that represent the intensity of the sound at a certain moment,
 - Once upon a time speech recognition systems were built to work on “phonemes” but now that is not necessary because it is possible to process the audio data as it is.
 - One way to build speech recognition systems is by inputting the audio clips into the bidirectional layer and the hidden layer will output the text.
 - Another way is to use CTC (connectionist temporal classification) cost for speech recognition: as a forward would say that so many language models have a much bigger input than the output, so for that the model could repeat some characters and then apply the rule “collapse repeated characters not separated by blank”

- Trigger word detection: some famous systems are amazon echo, google home, baidu dueros, these systems work by inputting the audio and outputting zeros all the time except when it hears the trigger word it output a one, or as an improvement it outputs a set of few ones.

- **Transformers:**

- As the complexity of the task increases so as the complexity of your model.
- Unlike RNN and sequential models, transformers allow you to ingest many words at the same time rather than processing it one at a time.
- The major innovation of transformers is combining the “attention” and “CNN”.
- Looking at the RNN network we see that the layer takes one word at a time while CNN takes many words (or pixels) at a time which gives the ability to process things in parallel.
- There are two attention network types:
 - Self-attention: computes representation for all the words in a sentence at the same time.
 - Multi-head attention: simply a for loop over the self-attention process. Which results in many versions of the representations.
- **Self-attention:** to calculate the attention for each word we will associate each word with three values: (query, key and value) think of it in terms of a database concept.
 - To find out what is most related to a certain word in the sentence we inner product the query of the word with the keys of each other word in the sentence
 - Then we multiply these products with the corresponding values, and sum all of them up to get the attention of the word
 - Query: let’s you ask a question about a certain word.
 - Key: looks at all the other words and by the similarity to the query give you the answer to the query question
 - Value: tell how the key should be represented by the query
- **Multi-headed attention:** each time you calculate self-attention for a sequence it is called a head.
 - In multi-head you repeat the same self-attention calculation several times to answer different questions, for example the first head asks about the place mentioned in the sentence and the second asks about the time in the sentence.
 - Adding more heads will enable you to calculate a richer representation for the sentence
 - After calculating the heads in a for loop (one after the other) or in parallel (all at the same time) you concatenate them and multiply them with w_0 .
- **The transformer network:**

- Encoder which is usually repeated 6 times in a network.
 - First start by passing the sentence embedding into the multi-head attention network.
 - Pass the output of the multi-head attention into a feed-forward neural network, which helps determine what interesting features there are in the sentence.
- Decoder which also get repeated for 6 times usually
 - We input what we already have translated to a multi-head attention network and the output gets fed into a second multi-head attention network.
 - The second multi-head attention network gets the output of the first one and the output of the encoder and produces a representation that gets fed into a feed forward neural network.
 - And the output of the decoder gets fed into a softmax layer to predict one word at a time
- **Bells and whistles** for the transformer network:
 - Positional encoding of the input: by using a combination of sin and cos equations that gets added to the input at each of the encoder and the decoder, and help tell where in the sentence the word appears, and these embedding gets passed through the network with residual connections, also the transformer uses batch norm layer to help pass the positional embedding through the whole network, also use layers called (add & norm) which is similar to batch norm and it helps speed up learning
 - Masked multi-head attention: it is used only during the training process where you use a dataset of correct translation to train the transformer, and what happens in training is not predicting one word at a time, but the masked network blocks a part of the sentence and pass it to the network for it to try to predict the missing part